

Faculty Interaction with International Students: Localisation of Cornell University Survey in Chinese University

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Abstract

Background / Context: *The article is devoted to the application of Cornell University Survey to the faculty interaction with international students in a Chinese university; take Jiangsu University, for example, the definition of formal and informal relations between them and teachers' assessment of the effectiveness of communication. It identifies based on the data gained because of the study, factors that support, develop or block the interaction between teachers and international students.*

Purpose of Study: *This study examines the data on the nature and frequency of the freelance interactions of teachers with international students in Jiangsu University, focusing on factors that support, develop, or, on the contrary, hinder the communication between teachers and international students.*

Research Design: *The study applied a multimodal research design using the conduct of quantitative research methods through the questionnaire of teachers.*

Findings / Results: *The findings of the study show that the most effective way of interaction between international students and teachers is personal communication.*

Conclusions: *The study makes several conclusions. First, that extracurricular communication helps teachers to understand each student and all students better. Second, almost all teachers supported informal conversation. Third, the majority of the faculty changed their approach to teaching and counseling and felt themselves to be part of the university community.*

Keywords: *international students, the program of adaptation of international students, the interaction of faculty with international students, international student education in China, the education system in China*

Introduction

The world is intensively developing interstate educational contacts, and the internationalisation of education allows student exchanges to move in all directions, not only just from east to west, but from less advanced to more developed areas making the number of a younger generations pursuing education outside their own country increasing as a result.

History of the Chinese Education System

China enjoys the world's most extensive educational system with 260 million pupils and over 15 million teachers in approximately 514,000 schools (China's National Statistics Bureau, 2014), except for graduate schools, China's education system not only is immensely but diverse.

Education for international students in New China took off in the 1950s attracting students from all across the world who have just been studying in the country, for well over a century, making trip to China in continually increasing numbers that have steadily increased in connection with significant national and international events. According to statistical data, over 41,000 international students of all types come from 125 countries across the world in the 1995-1996 academic year, such as trainees focusing entirely on languages learning, undergraduates, postgraduates, doctoral students, general trainees, advanced trainees, researchers and all kinds of short - term training programs.

China is also boosting the leading number of students studying abroad and has quickly become one of the best destinations for international students Wei (2013) securing its place among the world's leading ten (10) leading study destinations for international students ' choice reflecting an increase of 10.5 percent over 2016 within its long-term goal of hosting 500,000 students by 2020.

The growth of this tremendous leap has reflected in the continued expansion of the scheme of scholarships, the dominant Chinese economy and the relative affordability of Chinese higher education. Gaining an important factor in China's growing share of international students with two-thirds of students from China's "One Belt, One Road Initiative" a massive trade and foreign investment program linking markets along the traditional Silk Road trade routes throughout Asia, Africa, and Europe according to ICEF (2017).

International students' adaptation

To successfully organise the educational process for students is necessary to take into account that when they enter an international university; they fall into the unfamiliar socio-cultural, linguistic and national environment to which they are to adapt. Therefore, the success of their training at first is closely linked to the solution of adaptation problems. It compels international students, having a specific ethnic and psychological characteristic, to overcome all sorts of mental, social, moral, religious barriers, to master new types of activity and forms of behaviour.

In brief, most students will feel uncomfortable experiencing cultural shock; they may experience feelings of loneliness, disorientation, anxiety, alienation, resentment, and even feelings of helplessness or depression Chen (1999) & Kohls (1984).

Adapting international students to new socio-cultural conditions when admitted to a higher education institution is a fundamental factor determining the effectiveness of the educational process in most cases. Younger generations who pursue an education away from their country of origin find themselves in a problematic situation which reflects a severe life test. It forces them not only to master a new type of activity - to study at a higher educational institution to prepare for a future profession but also to adapt to an unfamiliar sociocultural space.

To solve international student adaptation problems universities in China are doing significant work aimed at improving the interaction between teachers and students, and trying to establish the most favourable environment for this.

The object

The object of this study is the program of adaptation of international students at Jiangsu University.

The subject

Is the study of the interaction of teachers with international students, the definition of formal and informal links between them, and the evaluation of their effectiveness by teachers.

Literature review

Faculty definitively has an essential impact on what students know about their studies and the whole world. The interaction between students and teachers has been an important research topic for many decades. The main criteria for assessing communication are the number of contacts, their content (thematic focus) and quality. Many studies prove the importance of each of these factors and the close connection with the successful adaptation and learning activities of students. In the analysis of Anaya and Cole (2001), made a conclusion about the close relationship between the progress of students, communication with teachers. They also found that the content of communication between students and teachers, as a rule, is more focused on academic topics than on personal ones, but that almost all types of interaction had a significant positive impact on students' assessments. In a study by Lundberg (2004), which examined the quality, quantity, and nature of interactions, the most decisive factor was called quality. Terenzini (1980) and Endo (1982) found in their study that the

frequency of interaction between teachers and students directly affects academic performance. Kuh and Hu (2001) investigated the rate of different types of student-teacher interactions and found that the most common kind of communication between students and teachers was strongly related to the course and concluded that students could get more from more significant interactions. Any interaction is beneficial for students, but the push for individualised communication can contribute to more achievement and student satisfaction. It devotes numerous to the study of formal and informal interactions, and the widespread virtual method of interaction in recent years. Informal interaction does not have to occur regularly, but it can have more impact on students than the formal interaction Lamport (1993); (Pascarella, 1980).

However, the interaction of teachers in the classroom with students can also be important. Tinto (1997) argues that classroom interaction is just as important as extracurricular interaction because the percentage of students who experience interaction in the classroom will be much higher. (Tinto (1997); Pascarella & Terenzini (2005)).

The possibility of virtual communication gives new opportunities for interaction between the teacher and the student. At present, the use of electronic mail is one of the main components of the debate on the impact of the interactive experience. The positive aspects of online communication can be attributed to the simplicity of contacting an instructor Haworth (1999), a simple entry point for students to worry about an approaching instructor Kelly (2001), and improved faculty perception of accessibility and responsiveness Jaasma and Koper (1999). However, Haworth (1999) found that students were more likely to use email as an alternative to face-to-face communication rather than as a Supplement. If students use emails to get answers to their questions, they are less likely to have extended interaction with teachers on topics other than explaining class topics or assignments.

Method

Research Model

This was contacted by using quantitative research through questionnaires for faculty members. Professor Xinchao li created the presented questionnaire based on the research paper finding of “Survey of Faculty Interaction with Undergraduate Student” by the Institutional Research and Planning of the Cornell University Fall 2004.

The presented questionnaire was transformed to apply to the Chinese educational environment, which was suitable for Jiangsu University.

Participants

Jiangsu University (JSU), from which 67 faculty members who taught international students pursuing academic degrees during spring term 2017, took part in the survey. Out of 67 teachers, 5 were single (never married, separated, divorced, or widowed) (7.5%) and 62 were married or living with a partner (92.5%).

Data Analysis

The response for each of the 67 faculty members who took part in the survey were input into SPSS one after the other and then individually analyzed on a group basis. First a descriptive frequency was conducted on each of the various variables to make the interpretation easier, like marital status, preference of interactions, role of faculty involvement in students studies, frequency of interaction and average hours per week spent with students, (role, activity impact, agreement level) of out-of-class interaction, activity of communication frequency and the number of publication by a faculty member. A one way analysis variance (ANOVA), a one-tailed independent group t-test to analyze the data.

This research is aimed at:

Mainly to understand the nature and frequency of out-of-class interactions between faculty members and undergraduate students, the factors supporting or inhibiting these interactions and the impact of these interactions on members of the faculty.

The study's objectives:

To identify factors that support, develop, or, on the contrary, block the interaction of teachers and international students.

The practical importance:

This study is directed to, in precise, to determine the optimal ways to support international students, their adaptation to the new living conditions and the characteristics of the social, cultural environment of China (or the province where the university is established). The process of social adaptation is complicated by the fact that the trained foreigners represent the community, combined by internal connections from culture, language, national consciousness, and interests related to a system of prevailing attitudes, values and norms Kupriyanov et al. (2015); Masalimova (2016).

Results of the study

The purpose of the study is to obtain data on the nature and frequency of the freelance interactions of teachers with international students at Jiangsu University.

RQ1: What are the most common ways of communication between teachers and international students?

Communication strategies are not only essential when considering the achievement of educational goals, but they are also crucial within functioning instructional teams.

For effective communication to take place, two people must communicate with each other as individuals instead of interacting based on student and teacher roles.

According to the results of the research, the most effective way of interaction between international students and teachers is a personal communication, and it has a stimulating effect on communication. The most usual methods of communication with international students are (see Table 1):

(i) Individual interaction with each student. 52.3% of teachers responded that they prefer it., (ii) Virtual communication via email or messages. This method of communication is mostly favourable by 63.2% of teachers. , (iii). Meetings with students at a set time in the office are preferred by 67.2% of teachers, (iv) Meetings with students before and after classes - 64.0%.

Table 1

Per cent frequency of stimulating role of interactions between faculty and undergraduate international students(N=67)

		Response Percent (%)	
		Agree	Strongly Agree
Preferences	Prefer to have individual communication with international students	3	49.3
	Prefer to have virtual communication, either via email or texting	8	55.2
	Prefer to meet with international students during designated office hours in my office	0	67.2
	Prefer to meet with international students before or after classes	3	61

Prefer not to communicate with individual international students	8.0	0	18
Prefer to communicate only with the monitor of the class	.5	3	4.5
Prefer to only communicate prior to an exam or submission of assignment	9.0	0	39

Note: The least Preference of interaction with students is 8% for “to communicate only with the monitor of the class”

Only 18.0% of teachers answered that they prefer not to communicate individually with international students; 8.0% prefer to communicate only to class monitors. 39.0% of teachers prefer to limit communication to prepare students for examinations and to check homework, excluding other issues from the range of discussed problems.

The willingness of most instructors to communicate informally is an indispensable factor in adapting international students who face new living conditions. The responses of the teachers suggest that personal communication with international students are favourable.

RQ2: What is the effectiveness of different ways of interaction between international students and teachers?

Researchers have shown that reticent students communicate less in class or not at all than their non-reticent counterparts Daly (1997). Faculty encourages students to interact through a virtual form of communication so that reticent students may have a vehicle for interacting. There may be a potential drawback to assisting reserved students in relying on e-mail, text to communicate with a faculty, by losing opportunities to develop or improve on their oral communication skills. Virtual communication can foster a closer relationship between teachers and students with even a possibility of increasing face-to-face interaction down the road.

The answers to those questions were as follows after analysing the leading roles that teachers played in communicating with international students (see Table 2):

Table 2
Percent of the role of teachers in communicating with foreign students

Role Category	N	Response Percent (%)	
		Yes	No
Faculty Advisor	67	31.3	68.7
Advise or supervise undergraduate international students working on faculty research project	67	16.4	83.6
Advise or supervise undergraduate international students working on student research project	67	10.4	89.6
Supervise undergraduate international students employed in non-research-related jobs	67	26.4	73.6
Serve on an academic community that includes undergraduate international students	67	14.9	85.1
Freshman book discussion group leader	67	16.4	83.6
Supervisor of undergraduate teaching assistants	67	18.0	82.0
Affiliated with student organization or club	67	16.4	83.6
Faculty in Residence	67	13.4	86.6
Affiliate with international students’ self-sponsored Life Builder Conference or affiliated with College Newsletter	67	11.0	89.0
Affiliated with Sino-foreign association	67	13.4	86.6

Note: “Advise or supervise undergraduate international students working on student research project” is the least percent responses accounting for 10%

The most common task in interacting with students is the faculty adviser. It accounts for 31% of the interviewed teachers. In the role of supervisors for international students who were not involved in any research, employed 26% of teachers,

Teachers, who supervise undergraduate international students working on the faculty research project, serve on an academic community that includes undergraduate international students, participate or lead the freshman book discussion, supervise of undergraduate teaching assistants or are affiliated with a student organisation or club account for approximately 16%.

Fewer respondents (around 10%) work as advisors or supervisors for undergraduate international students working on students’ research project, involved in students’ housing and residential life, affiliate with international students’ self-sponsored Life Builder Conference or affiliated with Jiangsu University Newsletter called “Olive,” or affiliated with Sino-international association.

RQ3: What is the frequency and duration of contacts between teachers and international students?

The study revealed that each role determines the frequency and duration of contacts between teachers and international students when identifying the rate of meetings between teachers and international students, with the exemption of Faculty Advisor and curator of international students who stay in contact 1-3 times a month or more frequently. As seen in Table 3 in relation to the stylized-like questions were measured as follows once or twice a term=1, once or twice a month=2, once a week=3 and twice a week or more=4 for frequency of interaction and the average of hours per week accounting for less than 1 hour=1, 1 to 2 hours=2, 3-5 hours =3 and more than 5 hours = 4, respectively.

Table 3
Frequency of interaction and the average hours per week. (N= 67)

Role Category	N	Frequency of Interaction		Average Hours Per Week		
		Sometimes	A lot	N	Few Hours	Serval Hours
Faculty Advisor	14	10	4	11	7	6
Advise or supervise undergraduate international students working on faculty research project	10	9	1	10	7	3
Advise or supervise undergraduate international students working on student research project	11	11	0	8	6	2
Supervise undergraduate international students employed in non-research-related jobs	13	12	1	11	9	2
Serve on academic community that includes undergraduate international students	10	10	0	10	9	1
Freshman book discussion group leader	11	10	1	7	7	0
Supervisor of undergraduate teaching assistants	9	8	1	7	7	0
Affiliated with student organization or club	9	9	0	8	8	0
Faculty in Residence	10	10	0	10	8	2
Community Advisor (or dorm assistant)	7	6	1	6	6	0
Affiliate with international students’ self-sponsored Life Builder Conference or affiliated with College Newsletter	7	7	0	8	8	0
Affiliated with Sino-foreign association	8	8	0	8	8	0

Note: Percent responses “Frequency of interaction” and “Average ours per week”.

The responses for the frequency of interaction and the average of hours per week were recorded by combining the responses of once or twice a term, once or twice a month into “Sometimes” with once a week, twice a week

or more as “A lot”. On the other hand, the average hours per week recorded into “Few Hours” or “Serval Hours”. 4 out of 67 faculty members enjoy the role of “faculty advisor” spending on average 3-4 hours or even more per week with undergraduate international students. 12 out of 67 take the part of “Supervise undergraduate international students employed in non-research-related jobs” by spending a few hours of their valuable time with international undergraduate students.

RQ4: What functions are most often performed by teachers in communication with international students?

The primary contacts between teachers and international students are carried out within the framework of the curriculum; however, some teachers take part in extra-curricular activities. The question emphasis on observation and also the act of “doing”. Faculty members reported on performing ten events with the following responses ranging from not involved=0, once or twice a term=1, once or twice a month=2, once a week=3, and several times a week or more=4. The responses were recorded in three Likert scales being “Sometimes”, “Hardly Ever” and “A lot”.

The outliers for the responses was “Not involved” with the remaining answers sum up to derive at the percent for each activity: 21% accounted for the majority of participants got involved “Organized or participated in orientation activities” which represent “a lot”.

15% accounted for both “had coffee or dined with undergraduate international students in a cafe or restaurant,” and “participated in an extracurricular presentation or workshop with undergraduate international students,” respectively. When it came to “participated in meetings of international student clubs or organisations,” and “hosted international students in your home (e.g., for a meal or social function)” it accounted for less involvement with 8% (as shown in Table 4).

Table 4
Percent of respondents in each extracurricular activities with international students (N= 67).

Activity Category	Percent activity response(% Faculty)					
	Not involved	Once or twice a term	Once or twice a month	Once a week	Several times a week or more	
Had coffee or dined with undergraduate international students in a cafe or restaurant	85.1	3.0	4.5	4.5	3.0	
Attended departmental functions for undergraduate international students (e.g., meals, meetings)	86.6	3.0	4.5	1.5	4.5	
Organized or participated in orientation activities	79.1	3.0	1.5	6.0	10.4	
Chaperoned an international student social function	89.6	3.0	4.5	1.5	1.5	
Participated in meetings of international student clubs or organisations	92.5	3.0	3.0	0.0	1.5	
Hosted international students in your home (e.g., for a meal or social function)	92.5	3.0	3.0	0.0	1.5	
Organised or attended an extracurricular field trip with an international student group or organisation	89.6	3.0	4.5	1.5	1.5	
Participated in an extracurricular presentation or workshop with undergraduate international students	85.1	3.0	4.5	4.5	3.0	
Accompanied undergraduate international students to an athletic competition	89.6	10.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Attended an art or cultural event with undergraduate international students	86.6	3.0	4.5	1.5	4.5	

Preferences of teachers on the frequency of contacts with foreign students

The process of adaptation of international students to a new socio-cultural environment takes place both in the framework of educational activities and during extracurricular events, which, in our opinion, contributes to the acceleration of this process, and also forms speech and sociocultural competence. The active participation of

teachers in extracurricular activities for international students makes it possible to solve problems of adaptation effectively and includes an international student in practical intercultural communication activities.

Also, it is vital to bear in mind that some factors may still induce students to feel inclined to seek out or communicate with faculty beyond the classroom. They may be students of the first generation who are still easily swayed by the faculty in general, in such a situation they may have no frame of reference regarding social guidelines during the first out - of -class interaction. Some faculty members make an early assignment for the student to come for a short visit during an office hour to provide extra encouragement. This often "lightens the mood" about future interactions. Certainly, out-of-classroom communications do offer a mixed blessing for faculty.

Interactions with students about the course or discipline can enhance both professionally and personally, but it can also be extremely (or even impractically) time-intensive, especially for a faculty with a large number of students. Because the roles and expectations of students and teachers in these conversations are much less structured and more diverse, Grasha (2002) they require careful attention to be successful.

Table 5

Percent of preferences in the frequency of contacts with international students (N=67)

Response Category	Would prefer more interaction	61.0
	Would prefer the current amount of interaction	30.0
	Would prefer less interaction	9.0
Total		100.0

Note: least preference in frequency of contact "would prefer less interaction" 9.0%

When answering a question about the preferences in the frequency of contacts with international students as seen in Table 5, the vast majority of teachers (61.0%) said that they would prefer to contact more often. 30.0% said they would prefer to leave the same number of contacts as before. Only 9.0% consider it necessary to reduce interaction.

RQ5: Which of the following experiences would you say influenced your frequency of communication with international students?

Fluency in English helps to increase the frequency of communication with international students; if there is a language barrier, the rate of contacts drastically decreases. Language difficulty will not only contribute to awkward situations in everyday routines but could also inhibit the capacity for social interaction Chen (1999). Another critical factor is the knowledge of the peculiarities of the national mentality of international students and the presence of intercultural competences of the teacher. Teachers who have had experience of communicating with representatives of other countries are more likely to have informal contacts with international students and rate this experience as positive. Ignorance of the traditions and customs of other nations, lack of experience with international students reduces the number of contacts. It is noteworthy that the family and personal obligations of teachers do not have any influence on the rate of connections with international students. Only two of the respondents showed this factor as unfavourable, which led to a reduction in the incidence of communication (see Table 6).

Table 6

Frequency of factors affecting faculty interaction with international students. (N=5)

		Frequency Responses		
		Negative Effect	No Effect	Positive Effect
Communication	English proficiency	2	6	8
	Prior departmental engagements	3	7	6
	Organised or participated in	2	8	6

orientation activities			
Family or personal engagements	1	12	3
Inter-cultural competences	3	5	8

The null and alternative hypotheses are spelled out below:

H_{null}: Effect of Communication Frequency does not affect the agreement level.

H_{alt}: Effect of Communication Frequency does affect the agreement level.

Interpretation derived from (Table 7, Table 8, Table 9, Table 10) :

To determine the effect of communication frequency influenced, the extent to which participants in the study agreed on, a one-way analysis of variance was conducted. The results showed that the null hypothesis should be rejected and that effect on communication frequency had a significant effect on the extent to which participants agreed with English proficiency, departmental engagements, organised or participated in orientation activities, family or personal engagements and inter-cultural competencies, $F(2,12) = 9.65, p < .05$. To determine which specific groups differ from one another, a Turkey test was conducted. The results of that analysis showed that the negative effect ($M = 2.20, SD = .83$) and positive effect ($M = 6.20, SD = 2.04$) effect of communication frequency did not differ from one another. However, the no effect produced significantly more on agreement level ($M = 7.60, SD = 2.70$) than either the no effect or negative effect on communication frequency, $p < .05$.

Table 7

Descriptives Result Extracted from SPSS

Agreement Level	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
					Negative Effect	5		
No Effect	5	7.60	2.702	1.208	4.25	10.95	5	12
Positive Effect	5	6.20	2.049	.917	3.66	8.74	3	8
Total	15	5.33	3.016	.779	3.66	7.00	1	12

Table 8

ANOVA Result Extracted from SPSS

Agreement Level

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	78.533	2	39.267	9.656	.003
Within Groups	48.800	12	4.067		
Total	127.333	14			

Table 9

Multiple Comparisons Result Extracted from SPSS

Dependent Variable: Agreement Level

Tukey HSD

(I)	Effect of(J)	Effect of Mean	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval
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Communication Frequency	Communication Frequency	Difference (I-J)			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Negative Effect	No Effect	-5.400*	1.275	.003	-8.80	-2.00
	Positive Effect	-4.000*	1.275	.022	-7.40	-.60
No Effect	Negative Effect	5.400*	1.275	.003	2.00	8.80
	Positive Effect	1.400	1.275	.533	-2.00	4.80
Positive Effect	Negative Effect	4.000*	1.275	.022	.60	7.40
	No Effect	-1.400	1.275	.533	-4.80	2.00

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 10
Agreement Level Result Extracted from SPSS

Tukey HSD

Effect of Communication Frequency	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Negative Effect	5	2.20	
Positive Effect	5		6.20
No Effect	5		7.60
Sig.		1.000	.533

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 5.000.

RQ6: What is the impact of informal communication with students on teachers?

At a certain point when asked, about the level of impact on teachers of informal interaction with international students the questions were measured in a Likert frequency of the scale with listing not at all=1, a little=2, some=3, A lot=4 and Not Applicable=5. It was recorded by grouping Not at all/A little as “Rarely”, some and a lot as a “Serval” with Not Applicable being outlined.

All teachers confirmed that extra-curricular communication helped them to better understand the individuality of each student, and all students in general (Table 11). Almost all teachers have changed teaching and counseling through this informal communication (12.7%,11.0%) and felt themselves a part of the university community, which accounted for (12.2%). Many of them believe that they have been professionally rewarded and that this will help them in career growth and promotion, which accounted for (9.9% and 5.5%).

Table 11
Percent of the impact of informal faculty communication with students(N=18)

Impact of informal communication	Response Percent (%)	
	Rarely	Very Often
I have a better understanding of the undergraduate international students with whom I have interacted.	0.0	14.9
I have a better understanding of undergraduate international students in general.	2.4	14.4

I have modified my approach to teaching.	4.8	12.7
I have modified my approach to advising.	11.9	11.0
I have enhanced my dossier for tenure or promotion.	14.3	5.5
I have enriched my life.	21.4	8.8
I feel more a part of the university community.	9.5	12.2
I have been professionally rewarded for this involvement.	21.4	9.9
	14.3	10.5
I have increased the difficulty of balancing personal and professional demands on my time.	0.0	14.9
I have a better understanding of the undergraduate international students with whom I have interacted.		
Total	100.0	100.0

Note: least percent responses of impact of informal communication. “Rarely” is 2.4% and “Very often” being 5.5%

Findings null and alternative hypotheses

- H_{null} The mean response score is given to a rarely impact of Out-of-Class Interaction source will be greater than or equal to the mean response score is given to a very often impact of Out-of-Class Interaction source
- H_{alt} The mean response score is given to a rarely impact of Out-of-Class Interaction source will be less than the mean response score is given to a very often impact of Out-of-Class Interaction source

Table 12
Group Statistics

	Impart of Interaction	Out-Of-ClassN	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Response	Rarely	9	4,67	3,240	1,080
	Very Often	9	20,11	5,231	1,744

Table 13
Independent Samples Test Result Extracted from SPSS

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	fort-test for Equality of Means
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		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	(2-Mean Diff.	Std. Diff.	Error95% Interval	Confidence of the Difference
										Lower Upper
Response	Equal variances assumed	1,170	,296	-7,530	16	,000	-15,444	2,051	-19,792	-11,096
	Equal variances not assumed			-7,530	13,352	,000	-15,444	2,051	-19,864	-11,025

From Table 11 and Table 13, It shows the level of impact of out-of-class interaction. The result showed that, the mean of response score given to a rarely, very often impact of out-of-class interaction was 4.67 (M = 4.67, SD = 3.24) and 20.11 (M = 20.11, SD = 5.23) respectively. From this result, a one-tailed independent group t-test was conducted, which showed that, the difference between the means was significant $t(16) = -7.53, p < .05$ showing that the null hypothesis should be rejected and conclude that very often produces more response on the impact of out-of-class interaction than rarely response sources.

RQ: 7 What is the evaluation of factors affecting interaction with international students?

Interaction with their faculty is one of the most influential factors in the success of students. According to Joosten (2012), student-faculty interaction outside the classroom can take many forms: in-person or online during office hours, Davis (2009) email exchanges, club counseling, volunteer opportunities, and small group meetings are just a few examples. For many—especially those in massive lecture courses—these more individualised communications offer the broadest kind of learning experiences by empowering students to ask questions related to their daily struggles and interests, take personal responsibility for their intellectual development, and make more personal connections with their teachers.

While investigating the factors influencing their communication, a 5 level of agreement were generated with completely disagree=1, disagree=2, neutral=3, agree=4 and completely agree=5. The responses were then codified into three levels of an agreement being “low agreement=1”, “neutral=2” and “high agreement=3”.

Table 14
Percent of the frequency of factors affecting faculty interaction with international students.

	Percent of Frequency		
	Low Agreement	Neutral	High Agreement
My teaching obligations leave little or no time for out-of-class contact with students	39.5	28.9	31.6
My research obligations leave little or no time for out-of-class contact with students.	39.5	34.2	26.3
I am primarily involved with graduate students.	43.6	30.8	25.6
I am not familiar with opportunities for out-of-class involvement.	42.1	34.2	23.7
My family leaves little or no time for out-of-class contact with students.	48.7	30.8	20.5
My travel and consulting responsibilities leave little or no time for out-of-class contact with students.	69.2	28.2	2.6
I think out-class contact with students is a less important part of the faculty role than research or teaching.	53.8	23.1	23.1
My department is not supportive of this type of involvement.	62.2	32.4	5.4
I have offered opportunities for out-of-class interaction, but students have not taken me up on them.	23.7	47.4	28.9
I have not received adequate orientation for participating in out-of-class roles with students.	24.3	37.8	37.8
I find it difficult to facilitate a meaningful informal exchange with students.	40.5	32.4	27.0
The University ignores or only minimally rewards faculty efforts at out-of-class interaction with students.	15.8	39.5	44.7
It is difficult to see international students in person; they prefer to communicate via e-mail or the Internet.	31.6	31.6	36.8
Faculty peers would assess my professional performance negatively if I spent too much time on out-of-class contact with students	52.6	34.2	13.2

Note: Percent responses of the level of agreement.

Table 14 shows the most significant factors of communicating with international students being:

(i) Preferences of students to communicate with teachers virtually (It is difficult to see international students in person; they prefer to communicate via email or the Internet). On an agreement level, 36.8%, 31.6% were in a high and low agreement, respectively, while answer to 31.6% were neutral. , (ii) The lack of motivation (the University ignores or only minimally rewards the efforts of teachers in a freelance interaction with international students), it shows that the majority of the faculty members were in high agreement of 44.7%, and fewer did not agree over lack of motivation from the university which accounted for 15.8% and the remaining 39.5% choosing neutral. , (iii) The lack of practical skills (I did not receive adequate training for participation in extra-curricular roles with international students) higher and lower agreement record the same response accounting for 37.8% respectively and neutral response is 24.3% ., (iv) The desire of the students themselves to go to informal contacts (I offered opportunities for outside class interaction, but the students did not want to). These showed less response of high agreement of 28.9%, teachers neither agreeing nor disagreeing accounted for a higher response of 47.4% and those who choose low agreement was 23.7%. , (v) No time for informal contacts (My teaching responsibilities practically do not leave time for extracurricular contacts with students). 31.6% showed high agreement, 39.5% disagreed with the question, and 28.9% choose to be neutral.

Findings for Null and alternative hypothesis:

H_{null}: Out of Class, interaction does not affect agreement.

H_{alt}: Out-of-Class interaction does affect agreement.

A one-way analysis of variance was extended on to determine whether out-of-class interaction influenced the extent to which participants in the study agreed on. Its analysis that, the null hypothesis should be rejected and that out-of-class interaction had a significant effect on the extent to which participants agreed with the message, F (2,39) =7.83, p <. 05. To be able to determine the specific group differs from one another, a Tukey test was conducted and as a result of analysis indicated that the high agreement (M = 9.43, SD = 4.45) and neutral agreement (M = 12.64, SD = 2.09) level of agreement conditions did not differ from one another. However, on the other hand, the low agreement source produced significantly more (M = 16.00, SD = 5.81) than either the neutral or high agreement, p <.05. (Table 15, Table 16, Table 17, Table 18)

Table 15

Table 12

Descriptives

Out-of-Class Interaction

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval		Minimum	Maximum
					for Mean			
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Low Agreement	14	16,00	5,805	1,551	12,65	19,35	6	27
Neutral	14	12,64	2,098	,561	11,43	13,85	9	18
High Agreement	14	9,43	4,450	1,189	6,86	12,00	1	17
Total	42	12,69	5,073	,783	11,11	14,27	1	27

Table 16

Table 13

ANOVA Result Extracted from SPSS

Out-of-Class Interaction

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	302,333	2	151,167	7,833	,001
Within Groups	752,643	39	19,299		
Total	1054,976	41			

Table 17

Multiple Comparisons Result Extracted from SPSS

Dependent Variable: Out-of-Class Interaction Tukey HSD

(I) Level of Agreement	(J) Level of Agreement	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Low Agreement	Neutral	3,357	1,660	,120	-,69	7,40
	High Agreement	6,571*	1,660	,001	2,53	10,62
Neutral	Low Agreement	-3,357	1,660	,120	-7,40	,69
	High Agreement	3,214	1,660	,142	-,83	7,26
High Agreement	Low Agreement	-6,571*	1,660	,001	-10,62	-2,53
	Neutral	-3,214	1,660	,142	-7,26	,83

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 18
Out-of-Class Interaction
Tukey HSD

Level of Agreement	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
High Agreement	14	9,43	
Neutral	14	12,64	12,64
Low Agreement	14		16,00
Sig.		,142	,120

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 14,000.

Table 19 The survey results reveal that the vast majority of teachers, along with teaching, conduct serious scientific work: 70.1% (M=1.70, SD=.46) published their work in scientific journals over the past 2 years, 37.3% of them wrote reviews of books and scientific articles (M=1.37, SD=.48), 35.8% worked on writing textbooks, monographs, and other research-based works accounting for (M=1.36, SD=.48), 38% made presentations at conferences and seminars (M=1.39, SD=.49).

Table 19
No. of Publication or Presentations for the last two years

Publication Category	N	M	SD	Response Percent (%)	
				Yes	No
Publication of articles in scientific journals	67	1.70	.461	70.1	29.9
Book Reviews	67	1.37	.487	37.3	62.7
Textbooks, monographs, research	67	1.36	.483	35.8	64.2
Presentations at scientific conferences and seminars	67	1.39	.491	38.8	61.2

Note: SD is Standard Deviation and M is Mean.

Only 29.9% of faculty did not publish scientific articles for two years of their work. 35.8% published 1 or 2 articles, 22.4% published 3 or 4 articles, and 11.9% of them published 5 or more articles. Thus, it can be stated that the research activities of teachers play an essential role in their work, and many successfully combine both spheres of activity: teaching and research (see Table 20).

Table 20

Frequency and percent of Faculty Publication.

	Frequency Responses				Response Percent (%)			
	None	1-2	3-4	5 or more	None	1-2	3-4	5 or more
Number of Publication	20	24	15	8	29.9	35.8	22.4	11.9
Total	67				100%			

*Least frequency and percent responses of publications by faculty is 8 and 12% respectively.

According to the research, the most effective interaction is carried out through joint activities: bright, memorable, appealing to international students, satisfying their individual needs. They provide the target, active, emotional unity of all participants of the program; allow rallying the collective and giving concrete, practical skills of behaviour in the society.

The overwhelming majority of the teachers who took part in the survey are family people (92%) and children (86%). When answering the question "How do you assess your current interests in work: research or teaching?", The majority of respondents (42%) noted equal interest in both teaching and research. 24% of teachers believe that both parties are interested in conducting research, and 22% answered that both parties are involved in teaching. Only 7% of survey participants noted a severe shift of interests towards scientific studies only, and only 5% of teachers give a clear preference for teaching.

Conclusions

For the successful process of teaching international students, all conditions must be created so that any of them can feel necessary and indispensable, a part of one big and united family. Also, students are in one of the most critical stages in a person's life. It is during this period that the final formation of the personality, the strengthening of the life position, takes place. It is during this period that the opportunity for young people to realise their creative potential, to learn to exist in a team, to try their hand at various fields of activity and precisely choose what will be most to their liking is significant for young people. To adequately address the problems as mentioned above, a comprehensive program is needed to adjust international students to the educational process which contributes to the harmonious development of the individual, to her self-improvement, the opening of the potential through a complex of activities and individual work with each international student. The program must perform socially adaptive functions, namely:

(i) Developing - creating conditions for the full-fledged social development of international students, stimulating positive changes in their personal development, supporting the processes of disclosure and self-expression of abilities; (ii) Protective - the neutralisation of negative environmental influences on the personality of the student and its development, raising the level of social security in the conditions of their stay in the university and hostel; (iii) Regulating - regulation of interpersonal relationships between students and their influence on the formation of the individual; (iv) Socialising - the introduction into the life of international students of the missing elements of life, speeding up the process of adaptation. ; (v) Corrective-correction of unfavourable influence on the behaviour and communication with students.

Following these tasks, it becomes evident that there is a need for close interaction of teachers with international students, often going beyond the educational process. It is a wide range of tasks on the adaptation of international students that requires an individual approach to each of them and leads to the need to establish informal, extra-curricular interactions. According to the study, it is extracurricular communication that helps teachers to better understand the individuality of each student, and all students in general. Almost all teachers have changed their approach to teaching and counselling through this informal communication and felt themselves part of the university community. The importance and significance of such contacts are apparent, and they cannot be underestimated. Also, many factors block the interaction between teachers and international students. They include: the preferences of students to communicate with teachers virtually, by email or via the Internet, the lack of motivation for teachers, their lack of practical skills for participation in informal contacts with international students, the unwillingness of the students themselves to go on informal contacts and the lack of time for informal contacts with teachers. In this regard, it is necessary to develop and implement a unique program for international students and a loyalty program for the teaching staff that could encourage and stimulate their contacts with international students. Extracurricular interactions can include a wide range of activities, such as academic counselling, monitoring of independent learning, working with international student clubs or academic organisations, and meals or visiting extracurricular activities with international students.

The field for further research

Since building effective communication requires the active participation of both parties, not only teachers, but also international students, we consider it appropriate to conduct a similar survey among students. As the results of this study showed, one of the main barriers to communication is the reluctance of students to make contact, their preferences to communicate virtually. Therefore, for a full understanding of the processes, it is necessary to study the attitude of students to interact with teachers, to identify barriers that prevent effective and fruitful interaction, and to determine the optimal roles of teachers that can help in the rapid adaptation of international students to the new conditions and social space of the University.

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